

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF VIOLATIONS OR MISAPPLICATION OF PROCEDURAL LEGAL NORMS IN THE REVIEW OF CIVIL COURT DECISIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the significance and functions of the grounds for annulment of judicial acts in the review of civil court decisions. It provides a detailed analysis of one specific type of such grounds — violations or misapplication of procedural legal norms. The article highlights the extent to which such violations can impact the review of civil court rulings. Furthermore, general conclusions are drawn based on the conducted analyses.

Keywords: decisions, procedural legal norms, functions of civil procedural law, substantive legal norms, court records.

Today, many measures are being taken to radically improve the judicial and legal system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and eliminate existing problems in it. Within the framework of these reforms, particular attention is being paid to ensuring the protection of the rights and interests of citizens and entrepreneurs through the courts, which is regarded as one of the most pressing issues. In this regard, the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026," outlines the goal of achieving a high standard of rule of law within the judicial system in line with global best practices. It emphasizes the importance of ensuring citizens' procedural rights, systematizing normative-legal acts regulating the

judiciary, and addressing other key objectives¹. These objectives include aligning national legislation with international principles. As part of this process, it is also necessary to address issues related to judicial documents, such as resolving specific problems within the appeals system of higher courts regarding judicial acts submitted by citizens and business entities. In particular, it is essential to improve, both theoretically and practically, the grounds based on violations or misapplication of procedural legal norms in the review of civil court decisions.

In the process of reviewing civil court decisions, the grounds for annulment of judicial acts are regarded as an institution of significant importance. This is because the clear and correct application and interpretation of these grounds ensure an objective reconsideration of judicial decisions. Within these procedures, the functions of civil procedural law play a crucial role. Article 2 of the Civil Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan outlines the functions of civil court proceedings². That is:

- proper, timely consideration and resolution of civil cases in order to protect the personal, political, economic and social rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, the rights and interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the rights and legally protected interests of enterprises, institutions, organizations, public associations and bodies of citizen self-government (hereinafter - organizations);

- promoting the strengthening of legality and law and order, ensuring democracy, social justice, peace and national accord among citizens;

- formation of a respectful attitude towards the law and the court.

The functions of civil proceedings, in addition to ensuring the rights and interests of citizens and entrepreneurs at the first instance, also guarantee their right to appeal the acts of the court of first instance.

In civil proceedings, the stage of review of judicial acts is of particular importance.

¹ Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60, January 28, 2022 – <https://lex.uz/docs/-5841063>

² Civil Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/docs/-3517337#-6716228>

Because civil proceedings are divided into several stages, each of which is considered as a separate institution in civil procedural law. A number of procedural scholars divide court stages into the following types:

- initiation of legal proceedings;
- preparation of the case for trial;
- consideration of the case in court (judicial proceedings);
- review of judicial acts;
- stages of execution of court documents³.

Now, based on the foregoing, it is necessary to dwell on the types of grounds for cancellation or amendment of judicial acts, which form the basis of the stage of reviewing civil judicial acts, and analyze each of them separately.

When overturning decisions of civil courts by higher instances, the courts rely on certain grounds. The grounds for the annulment of these judicial acts are strictly defined in civil procedural legislation. That is, in accordance with Article 372² of the Civil Procedure Code, it is divided into the following types:

- incomplete clarification of circumstances relevant to the case;
- unprovenness of the circumstances that the court considered established, having significance for the case;
- inconsistency of the court's conclusions, set forth in the judicial act, with the circumstances of the case;
- non-adoption by the court of a judicial act on the stated claim;
- violation or incorrect application of the norms of substantive and procedural law.

From the grounds for the cancellation of these judicial acts, grounds for violation or incorrect application of procedural law norms can be taken as a separate type.

Types of Grounds for Violation or Misapplication of Procedural Legal Norms.

³ Civil procedural law (questions and answers) [Text]: textbook / Khabibullayev Davlatjon Yulchiboyevich. - T.: TSUL Publishing House, 2023. - 336 p. Page 10

Article 372⁴ of the Civil Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides a detailed outline of the grounds for annulment of judicial acts resulting from the violation or misapplication of procedural legal norms⁴. According to this norm, they are subdivided into the following types:

1) the case was considered by the court with an unlawful composition or in violation of the rules of jurisdiction;

2) the case was considered by the court in the absence of any of the persons entitled to participate in the trial, who were not notified of the time and place of the court session;

3) violation of the rules of the language in which the proceedings are conducted during the consideration of the case;

4) the court has resolved the issue of the rights and obligations of persons not involved in the case;

5) when issuing a court decision, ruling, or decree, the rules on the secrecy of judicial deliberation have been violated;

6) the decision, ruling, or decree is signed by judges (judge) other than those who considered and resolved the case (judge);

7) a court decision, ruling, or decree may also be overturned if the minutes of the court session are not signed.

Since these grounds are listed in seven paragraphs of the Civil Procedure Code, they are taken as seven grounds. However, there are not seven, but eight bases here. Because the first paragraph of the first part of the above article contains two grounds, namely:

- the case was considered by the court in an unlawful composition;
- in violation of the rules on jurisdiction.

These two should be taken as two independent bases. Because both situations arise in two different situations, and the reasons for their occurrence are also different.

⁴ Civil Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/docs/-3517337#-6716228>

Concepts of violation or incorrect application of procedural law norms.

Violation or misapplication of these two concepts always comes together in procedural legislation. However, it is necessary to create separate definitions for these two concepts, to analyze which of the above grounds can lead to violation of the norms of procedural law and which can lead to incorrect application. Because, by distinguishing these concepts, it will be possible to find out in which case the decision can be overturned and in which case it can be changed.

Also, the grounds for violation or incorrect application of the norms of procedural law can be overturned or changed only if this leads to the incorrect adoption of a court decision. Based on this rule, the above-mentioned grounds can be divided into two groups. That is, the first group includes circumstances under which the decision can be overturned or amended, and the second group includes circumstances under which the decision can be overturned in any case.

In conclusion, in civil procedural law, the grounds for the annulment of judicial acts are divided into several groups, and these groups, in turn, are divided into several types. One of them is the grounds for violation or incorrect application of procedural law norms. Although these grounds are included in one general composition, they can be classified as grounds for the annulment of judicial acts arising from violations of the norms of general and special procedural law. This, in turn, is important for their in-depth analysis.

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